

DELIVERABLE 7.2

Technical Report

Preliminary Platform Development

Augusto Esteves, Gianni Tumedei,
Andrea Cristiano, Luiz Sachser, João Bravo

29 June 2026. Version 1.0

Funded by
the European Union

D7.2 Overview

PROJECT	RELISH
PROJECT NO.	101177427
WORKPACKAGE	WP7: SIMMERING – Development & Testing
DELIVERABLE	D7.2
VERSION NO.	1.0
DUE DATE	30/06/2026
SUBMISSION DATE	29/06/2026
TYPE	Public
AUTHOR(S)	Augusto Esteves, Gianni Tumedei, Andrea Cristiano, Luiz Sachser, João Bravo
REVIEWER(S)	H. Rosi Song, Janita Van Dyk
APPROVER	H. Rosi Song

Document history

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	CHANGES
0.1	25/05/2026	Augusto Esteves	Document creation
0.2	08/06/2026	Gianni Tumedei	Completed Section 2.3
0.3	19/06/2026	Andrea Cristiano	Completed Section 2.4
0.4	22/06/2026	Luiz Sachser	Completed Section 2.2
0.5	24/06/2026	João Bravo	Completed Section 2.5
0.6	25/06/2026	Augusto Esteves	Completed Sections 1.1, 2.1, Executive Summary
0.7	27/06/2026	H. Rosi Song, Janita Van Dyk	Internal Review
0.8	28/06/2026	Augusto Esteves	Implemented Revisions
0.9	28/06/2026	Janita Van Dyk	Formatting
1.0	29/06/2026	H. Rosi Song	Coordinator Approval and Final Submission

Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	PC	Project Coordinator
clCH	culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage	SoS	System of Systems
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	T[No.]	Task [No.]
EC	European Commission	UC[No.]	Use Case [No.]
GA	Grant Agreement	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

Legal disclaimer

RELISH is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101177427. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the

European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

Contents

D7.2 Overview	i
Document history	i
Abbreviations and acronyms	ii
Consortium	ii
Legal disclaimer	ii
Contents	iv
List of Figures	v
List of Tables	v
Executive Summary	vi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Description of the document	1
2 The RELISH Web Platform (T7.1)	3
2.1 UC1, T7.2: Food Memories	5
2.1.1 Introduction	5
2.1.2 Requirements	6
2.1.3 Summary	8
2.1.4 Architecture	9
2.1.5 Implementation	14
2.1.6 User Interface (UI) Walkthrough: Facilitator	15
2.1.7 Security, Data Sovereignty, and Governance	16
2.1.8 Deployment and Infrastructure	20
2.1.9 Architectural Trade-offs	20
2.1.10 Summary and Future Work	21
2.2 UC3, T7.3: Recipes' Digital Twin	23
2.2.1 Introduction	23
2.2.2 Modelling Intangible Cultural Heritage as a Digital Twin	24
2.2.3 Architecture	26
2.2.4 Implementation	27
2.2.5 Design Opportunities	28
2.2.6 Summary and Future Work	30
2.3 UC4, T7.5: Shopping Recommender: Seasonality and Preferred Cuisines	31
2.3.1 Introduction	31
2.3.2 System Design	32
2.3.3 Recommender	33
2.3.4 Interface Design	34
2.3.5 System Implementation	35
2.3.6 Summary and Future Work	35
2.4 UC5, T7.6: Youth Survey on Food Culture	37
2.4.1 Introduction	37
2.4.2 Architecture	38
2.4.3 Implementation	39
2.4.4 Summary and Future Work	41
3 Conclusions	43
Bibliography	44

List of Figures

Figure 1: The RELISH platform can be described as a System of Systems (SoS) architecture of multiple software systems described in this document (i.e., UCs).	3
Figure 2: The overview of the layered architecture of the Food Memories system.	10
Figure 3: An overview of our functional layers and data flow routes.	12
Figure 4: A photo data flow example in our Food Memories system.	13
Figure 5: A facilitator walkthrough of various UIs of our Food Memories system.	16
Figure 6: An overview of our Food Memories deployment using OpenStack.	19
Figure 7: The layered architecture of our recipe digital twin system.	25
Figure 8: Speculative interface mock-ups of the application concepts emerged from our focus group session. From left to right: the <i>Culinary Practice Observatory</i> and the <i>Collaborative Recipe Studio</i> .	28
Figure 9: Plots displaying <i>Italian cuisine</i> 's graph edge weights before normalisation (showing scale-free characteristics), applying a $1/k$ normalisation, and the log-normalisation used in the UC.	32
Figure 10: Our web application displaying the connections for cucumbers in <i>Japanese cuisine</i> . The ingredient recommendations are shown in the left column, while seasonality scores are shown in the right column.	33
Figure 11: Our Telegram bot interface for the ingredient recommender. <i>From left to right</i> : the user first receives a list of all seasonal items with their seasonality score, then chooses an ingredient and a cuisine from which to get recommendations.	34
Figure 12: The three-tier architecture of our surveys includes a security and privacy layer that spans the presentation, application, and storage tiers.	38
Figure 13: How our three surveys render responsively across desktop, laptop, and mobile devices.	40
Figure 14: <i>Left</i> : The Youth dashboard, mapping the geographic origin of respondents alongside a ranked list of countries. <i>Right</i> : The Narratives dashboard, offering a searchable reader for the "A Day in the Life in 2050" responses.	41

List of Tables

Table 1: Summary of our system's three-tier technology stack.	11
Table 2: Security vulnerability assessment for our Food Memories system.	17

Executive Summary

Deliverable 7.2 (D7.2) provides a technical overview of the ongoing design and implementation of the RELISH web platform under WP7. Operating within the broader Horizon Europe-funded RELISH project, the platform functions as a scalable repository for project data, dashboards, and models. It is built upon a System of Systems (SoS) architecture hosted on the IST institution's VMCloud private cloud infrastructure. This federated design ensures that multiple autonomous software systems can operate within strict data boundaries, maximising systemic fault tolerance while accommodating institutional data governance constraints and data sovereignty.

While a full report is due in September 2027 (M33), this document details the progress of four distinct, task-oriented use-cases (UCs) that demonstrate the platform's diverse capabilities. These include the Food Memories (UC1, T7.2) browser-based companion application designed to facilitate narrative cooking workshops, and the Recipes' Digital Twin (UC3, T7.4), which uses AI to model culinary recipes extracted from online social traces as living, evolving practices. Additionally, the report outlines the Shopping Recommender (UC4, T7.5), a graph-based tool integrating computational gastronomy with seasonality to promote sustainable grocery choices, and the Youth Survey on Food Culture (UC5, T7.6), a platform hosting three interactive dashboards to capture and analyse how young people relate to food identity and futures.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

This technical report for **Deliverable 7.2 (D7.2)** provides a snapshot of the iterative design and implementation work taking place in Work Package 7 (WP7), namely:

- The design and development of the **RELISH web platform**, a scalable repository of data, dashboards, and models that facilitates access to the information produced and gathered throughout the project.
- While a complete use-case (UC) report spanning activities across WP7 and WP8 is due in Month 33 (D8.1), these UCs help us demonstrate and iterate on the RELISH platform's capabilities and features. This technical report describes the ongoing design and development of four of seven UCs.

1.1 Description of the document

This document provides a detailed snapshot of the ongoing, iterative design and implementation of the RELISH web platform, under WP7. As part of the broader Horizon Europe-funded RELISH project – which seeks to strengthen the EU's culinary cultural heritage through digital innovation – the platform serves as a scalable repository of data, models, and interactive dashboards.

Architecturally, the RELISH platform operates as a **System of Systems (SoS)**. Rather than being a single monolithic application, it operates as a conceptual umbrella for multiple autonomous, task-oriented software systems deployed on VMCloud, a private cloud infrastructure. Each constituent system maps to an independent UC, maintaining its own isolated database tier and technology stack to ensure systemic fault tolerance, strict data governance, and data sovereignty.

While a complete use-case report is scheduled for M33, this technical report outlines the design, implementation, and future work for four of the seven UC under development:

Food Memories (UC1, T7.2) – A browser-based facilitator companion application designed to support two-day narrative and collaborative cooking workshops. The tool operationalises the consortium’s methodology by providing structured workshop agendas, participant management, and contextualised photo documentation while ensuring all sensitive participant data remains securely under institutional control.

Recipes’ Digital Twin (UC3, T7.4) – A novel system that adapts the “digital twin” paradigm for **culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage (ciCH)**. By using an AI-assisted pipeline to ingest and extract structured data from online social media traces (such as YouTube cooking videos), this system models recipes not as fixed artefacts, but as living, evolving cultural practices.

Shopping Recommender (UC4, T7.5) – Graph-based recommendation system built to promote sustainable and seasonal eating. Accessible via a Telegram bot and an interactive web dashboard, it integrates seasonality data with computational gastronomy networks to recommend coherent, culturally relevant ingredient pairings to users.

Youth Survey on Food Culture (UC5, T7.6) – A platform hosting three distinct online surveys (the Youth Survey, the Futures Survey, and the Futures Narratives Survey) to capture how young people understand their food practices and identity. Each survey is paired with a bespoke, interactive dashboard that allows analysts to explore responses through privacy-preserving visualisations and maps.

Together, these four systems allow the platform’s design to merge technological innovation with cultural heritage practices, offering digital tools that support social connection and sustainable culinary pathways.

2 The RELISH Web Platform (T7.1)

The RELISH platform leverages a **System of Systems (SoS) architecture**: a federated engineering paradigm in which multiple autonomous, task-oriented constituent systems pool their resources and capabilities to realise a collective, emergent value that a single component could hardly achieve independently (Mahmood 2016).

This SoS architecture is formally characterised by the operational and managerial independence of its constituent elements, their evolutionary development lifecycles, and their virtual or geographic distribution. Rather than a single, rigid runtime environment, the overarching platform offers a conceptual umbrella comprising distinct software systems that map to independent UCs.

Each constituent system (*i.e.*, UC) functions as an autonomous entity that undergoes its own compilation and deployment pipeline, maintaining a dedicated technology stack, business logic, and isolated database tier tailored to its domain requirements.

Figure 1: The RELISH platform can be described as a System of Systems (SoS) architecture of multiple software systems described in this document (*i.e.*, UCs).

Interoperability across the platform is strictly decoupled, relying on sparse, well-defined data exchanges to preserve absolute domain boundaries and prevent horizontal privilege escalation across systems. This design maximises systemic fault

tolerance – ensuring that a localised runtime failure remains contained – while accommodating institutional data-governance constraints and data sovereignty commitments by deploying across distributed, independent virtual machine environments.

The RELISH platform is deployed in VMCloud,¹ an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) platform and private cloud service hosted at our institution's (IST) data centres. This is entirely maintained by the IST's IT team using the open-source OpenStack software. An overview of our architecture is shown in Figure 1.

¹ <https://vmcloud.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/>

2.1 UC1, T7.2: Food Memories

2.1.1 Introduction

Food carries meaning well beyond nutrition. The dishes people cook, request, and remember are bound up with where they come from, who raised them, and how they have moved through the world.

UC1 on Food Memories treats this everyday entanglement of taste and biography as a route into cICH: rather than asking participants to describe a tradition from the outside, the workshops our system supports invite them to write, map, and cook their way into it, surfacing how a recipe can hold family history, migration, and a sense of belonging all at once. The Food Memories approach (see **D3.1: “RELISH Food Memories Report”**²) builds on a Danish community initiative that originally used creative writing and reflective conversation to help migrants and newcomers work through how their cooking changed or remained the same after leaving home (Savinetti et al. 2020).

RELISH’s premise is that **a recipe is never just a set of instructions**. Identifying a dish as belonging to a particular place or tradition may look simple on the surface, but it raises a harder question beneath the surface: How does one person’s memory of a meal relate to the larger, often anonymous, collective memory that is called a “national” or “regional” cuisine (Ricoeur 2002)? Food Memories answers this through narrative inquiry – eliciting individual perspective through dialogue, writing, and visual mapping on the understanding that telling a story is itself a way of making sense of experience (Wells 2011).

Because narrative inquiry is necessarily a shared activity between the person asking and the person answering, with both holding some responsibility for what gets explored (Heldke 1988), the workshops our system supports are designed to leave **room for participants’ own meanings** rather than sorting their stories into categories decided in advance (Josselson and Hammack 2021). Everyday storytelling about practice and experience is a rich evidence base for understanding how people act and relate to one another (J.Lewis and Hildebrandt 2019). This evidentiary weight that justifies building a dedicated digital toolkit around the method rather than relying on ad hoc notes and recordings.

However, writing alone tends to capture what participants can already put into words, leaving the more tacit, body-held side of cooking under-represented. This is why the Food Memories methodology pairs a narrative session with a hands-on cooking

² <https://zenodo.org/records/18889651>

session: preparing a dish gives participants a way to act out what they have just written about, exposing judgment calls—a pinch of salt here, a texture checked by touch there—that rarely make it into a written account (Heldke 1988).

Three pilots carried out by the consortium across May, June, and October 2025 tested this pairing in practice and progressively reshaped the Food Memories workshop design: early sessions that skipped the narrative day found that conversation during cooking stayed comparatively shallow, while the October pilot, which ran the full two-day sequence, produced markedly richer engagement once participants had already mapped and written about their memories beforehand.

The pilots also showed that a facilitator running the cooking session cannot simultaneously take detailed notes, which is why the workshop format settled on a two-role model — a facilitator who leads and an observer who documents — and why recipes are now agreed on collectively rather than supplied by a single participant, since a lone contributor tends to dominate the conversation while everyone else becomes a spectator.

2.1.2 Requirements

This pilot history motivates the system described in the remainder of this section, and several of the consortium’s own findings translate fairly directly into design requirements.

Challenge 1: Workshop facilitation prioritised over data gathering

The recurring observation that a facilitator cannot run the cooking session and take structured notes simultaneously. In some situations, facilitators’ record-keeping suffered. A system could integrate distinct facilitator and observer/participant roles rather than a single, undifferentiated login.

Challenge 2: Maintaining collective engagement

During workshops, when one participant was asked to supply “their” recipe, the rest of the group disengaged. The methodological design was resolved by moving to a collectively agreed-upon recipe. The supporting tool could likewise support a shared, group-level workshop record rather than a set of disconnected individual entries.

Challenge 3: Collecting and managing multimedia materials and textual data to allow comparability

The growing volume of material across the three 2025 pilots – memory maps, free-written narratives, field notes, co-created recipes, and photographs, gathered through whatever combination of paper, phone cameras, and shared folders happened to be on hand at each site – could be tracked informally when the Food Memories method was still confined to a single host institution. However, materials and data became harder to manage once the format moved towards repeated delivery at RUC, UMIL, ATU, and FA.

Comparing outputs across those sites depends on every facilitator following the same module sequence and timing, and on every photograph being traceable back to the day, phase, and module in which it was taken, rather than sitting in an undated camera roll. A system could be designed to facilitate secure and organised data entry.

Challenge 4: Securing potentially sensitive and personally identifiable data

Because the workshops also handle participants' food memories, family histories, and (in the case of migrant or minority participants) potentially sensitive material, the consortium's own ethical commitments around confidentiality and informed consent require a central, non-third-party-accessible location. However, this requires manually scanning and uploading data and setting user permissions. Each of these steps can introduce user error and potential data breaches. If a participant withdraws consent, facilitators must manually identify and remove the data and materials. A feature could facilitate data gathering, organising, uploading, and temporarily secure hosting on a single, secure server, with user roles that allow access, limit, and withdraw data/uploads.

Taken together, the Food Memories pilot-stage challenges set the brief for this UC, moving it away from a generic note-taking app. Our system needed to:

- Walk a facilitator through the workshop's own two-day, phase-by-phase structure instead of leaving the agenda in a printed script that is easy to drift from under time pressure;
- Register and annotate participants and activities – including the dietary needs, cultural background, and observational notes the methodology asks facilitators to track – without that record-keeping competing for the facilitator's attention during the cooking session itself;

- Capture and tag photographs of multimedia materials and activities at the point of use, organised by day, phase, and module, so that the visual material from one site remains comparable with another's months later;
- Keep and secure workshop data under the hosting institution's control rather than defaulting to a third-party cloud service until it is exported, and allow individual users (workshop participants) to delete or withdraw their uploads independently and anonymously.

These four needs — agenda fidelity, participant management, contextualised photo documentation, and institutional data sovereignty — correspond directly to the objectives and architectural commitments set out below.

2.1.3 Summary

This section documents the design, architecture, implementation, and evaluation of the Food Memories UC. The prototyped system is a **browser-based facilitator companion application** that supports the two-day Food Memories workshop methodology developed by the RELISH consortium.

The Food Memories workshop brings together participants to explore culinary memory, ICH, and speculative recipe-making through a structured sequence of activities combining narrative writing, memory mapping, collaborative cooking, and reflective tasting.

Our system operationalises this methodology by providing facilitators with a real-time digital console that mirrors the workshop's phased structure, whilst also collecting, managing, and preserving the documentary outputs of each session. This section can be summarised as follows:

- A description of the system's purpose and scope;
- The full layered architecture and key design choices;
- A component-by-component implementation account;
- An analysis of the trade-offs,
- Strengths and limitations of those choices;
- A treatment of security, data sovereignty, and governance;

- A data-flow walkthrough;
- A summary of future work.

2.1.3.1 Scope and Objectives

Our system pursues three operational objectives:

- Provide facilitators with a structured, module-by-module guide through each day's phases, including per-module timing, facilitation steps, required materials, and facilitation tips (*agenda navigation*);
- Allow facilitators to register, annotate, and export participant rosters, capturing dietary needs, cultural backgrounds, and observational notes (*participant management*);
- Enable capture, upload, and annotation of workshop photographs associated with specific sessions, phases, and modules, forming a persistent visual archive for each workshop instance (*photo documentation*).

A secondary objective is to demonstrate the RELISH platform's capacity to deploy small-scale, self-hosted software tools that operate within institutional data-governance constraints – a concern shared across all use cases in WP7.

2.1.4 Architecture

2.1.4.1 Overview

Our system follows a classic three-tier web application architecture, separated into a React-based single-page application (SPA) frontend, a Node.js/Express REST API backend, and a MongoDB document database (Table 1). The three tiers run as independent processes that communicate over HTTP. Figure 2 illustrates this high-level structure. The architecture deliberately avoids external cloud dependencies by defaulting to a locally running MongoDB instance and filesystem-based file storage. This reflects the RELISH project's commitment to data sovereignty: workshop data – including participant details and photographs – always remain under institutional control. Our design is, however, extensible: the storage layer can be pointed to a MongoDB Atlas cluster or an S3-compatible object store with only configuration changes, with no code modifications.

Figure 2: The overview of the layered architecture of the Food Memories system.

2.1.4.2 Layered Architecture

Expanding on the three-tier model, our system can be understood as five functional layers, adapted here for a workshop facilitation context (Figure 3).

Presentation Layer – We leveraged React 18 SPA bundled with Create React App (CRA). The entire application state – authentication context, workshop progress, participant roster, photo collection, timer state, checklist state – is managed client-side using React hooks (*useState*, *useEffect*, *useCallback*, *useMemo*, *useRef*). No external state management library (e.g., Redux) is used; the scope and depth of shared state do not warrant it. Tailwind CSS provides utility-based styling via a custom design token system (relish-ink, relish-accent, relish-paper, etc.) that reproduces the RELISH project’s visual identity throughout the application. Typography relies on two Google Fonts typefaces: DM Serif Display (headings) and Source Sans 3 (body text). Lastly, the SPA communicates with the backend exclusively through a simple *authFetch* wrapper that attaches JWT Bearer tokens to outgoing requests and transparently attempts to refresh the token on 401 responses before retrying. This design ensures that expired access tokens do not interrupt the facilitator’s session.

API and Business Logic Layer – The backend is an Express 4 application running on Node.js 20. It exposes five route namespaces:

- Authentication: sign-up, log-in, token refresh, log-out, and password reset;
- CRUD operations on the participant roster, scoped to the authenticated user’s role and workshop;
- Photo upload (via Multer multipart parsing), listing, and deletion, with file system cleanup on delete;
- Workshop lifecycle management: create, rename, assign facilitator, archive (facilitator), and hard-delete (admin);
- User listing, restricted to admin and facilitator roles.

Each route enforces authentication (*authentication middleware*) and role-based authorisation (*authorisation middleware*) before the business logic executes. Cross-cutting concerns – CORS, security headers, request logging, JSON body parsing, rate limiting – are applied as Express middleware at the application level.

Table 1: Summary of our system’s three-tier technology stack.

TIER	TECHNOLOGY	RESPONSIBILITY
Presentation	React 18, Create React App, Tailwind CSS	Renders the facilitator UI; manages all client-side state; communicates with the API over authenticated HTTP
Application	Node.js 20, Express 4, Multer, Mongoose	Implements business logic, authentication, authorisation, file handling, and REST endpoints
Data	MongoDB (local or Atlas), filesystem	Persists structured documents (users, participants, workshops, photo metadata) and uploaded image files

Data Access Layer – Mongoose 8 provides a schema-based object-document mapper (ODM) over MongoDB. Four domain models are defined:

- Email and password credentials, role (facilitator, participant, and admin), linked workshop, refresh-token hashes, and password-reset tokens;
- Name, linked facilitator, and archive metadata;
- Name, email, dietary requirements, cultural background, free-text notes, links to user and workshop documents;

- Filename, MIME type, file size, storage path, day/phase/module coordinates, caption, notes, links to participant and workshop documents, virtual *fileUrl*.

Relationships are modelled as MongoDB *ObjectId* references rather than embedded subdocuments, enabling independent querying of each entity type and efficient population (joins) where needed.

Figure 3: An overview of our functional layers and data flow routes.

Storage Layer – Uploaded images are stored on our server filesystem under a hierarchical path: *uploads/day-{N}/phase-{M}/{moduleId}/{timestamp}-{filename}*. The path encodes the pedagogical context of each photograph (day, phase, module), facilitating retrospective browsing and export. The storage module (*server/src/utils/storage.js*) handles directory creation, path building, and upload-root resolution from environment variables, decoupling the business logic from the physical storage location. Photo metadata – including the storage path – persists in MongoDB alongside a virtual *fileUrl* property that generates an authenticated API endpoint URL at serialisation time. Client code uses this endpoint rather than constructing file paths directly, ensuring that access control is enforced on every file download.

Client Caching and Preview Layer – Because file access requires authentication, the SPA cannot simply embed source URLs pointing at the server filesystem. Instead, it fetches each photo blob via the authenticated *authFetch* wrapper and converts it to an object URL (*URL.createObjectURL*), which is stored in a *photoPreviews* map keyed by photo ID. Object URLs are revoked when photos are removed from state, preventing memory leaks. This layer acts as an ephemeral client-side cache, trading memory for network efficiency within a session (Figure 4).

Figure 4: A photo data flow example in our Food Memories system.

2.1.5 Implementation

2.1.5.1 Technology Stack Rationale

The technology choices reflect several constraints: the need for rapid prototyping within a research project timeline, the requirement for self-hosted deployment on a facilitator's laptop, and alignment with the development team's existing expertise.

React and Create React App – React was selected for its component model, hook-based state management, and the large ecosystem of UI primitives available via libraries such as lucide-react (iconography) and Tailwind CSS (styling). Create React App provides a zero-configuration build pipeline suitable for the prototype stage. The decision to keep all states in a single top-level component (WorkshopTool) rather than adopting a global store (Context API, Zustand, Redux) was a deliberate trade-off: it simplifies debugging and avoids additional dependencies at the cost of prop-drilling depth. Refactoring to a context-based architecture is recommended if the component tree grows in the future.

MongoDB and Mongoose – MongoDB was chosen for its schema flexibility – participant records may carry optional fields (dietary, cultural, notes) that vary across workshops – and for the ease of embedding or referencing related documents. Mongoose adds schema validation and a clean query API on top of the native driver. The use of references (*ObjectId* foreign keys) rather than embedded documents for workshop, participant, and photo relationships reflects the need to query and update each entity independently (e.g., unassigning all participants from a deleted workshop without loading the workshop document).

JWT Authentication – Our system implements a dual-token authentication scheme: a short-lived (1-hour) access token transmitted as an HTTP authorisation header, and a long-lived (7-day) refresh token stored in an *httpOnly, SameSite=Lax* cookie. The access token carries the user's ID, email, role, and *workshopId* as claims, enabling the API to enforce role-based access control without an additional database lookup on every request. The refresh token is hashed before storage (SHA-256, no salt), preventing exposure of the raw token in the event of a database breach. Refresh token rotation is implemented: each use of a refresh token invalidates it and issues a replacement, limiting the window of opportunity for token replay attacks.

Multer File Handling – Multer (middleware for Node.js) and Express, handles multipart/form-data uploads with a custom *diskStorage* strategy that derives the destination directory from the day, *phaseIndex*, and *moduleId* fields in the request body, encoding pedagogical context directly into the filesystem hierarchy. File type

validation (*image/* MIME type only*) and a 10 MB size limit are enforced at the middleware level, before the file reaches the business logic layer.

Authentication and Authorisation – Three user roles are supported: participant (own workshop, read-only, and upload of own photos), facilitator (own workshop, full CRUD, and participants and photos in own workshop), and admin. Authorisation is enforced at the route level using the *authorise(...roles)* middleware and at the query level as well: facilitators' database queries are automatically scoped to their own *workshopId*, preventing horizontal privilege escalation even if the route-level guard is bypassed.

2.1.6 User Interface (UI) Walkthrough: Facilitator

The UI was designed for low-friction facilitation, ensuring that our system operates quietly in the background without disrupting the flow of workshop activities. Rather than requiring facilitators to navigate complex software workflows, the system presents the Food Memories methodology through a structured and intuitive digital environment that supports workshop delivery, participant management, and documentation. Figure 5 illustrates key views from the facilitator's single-page application (SPA), illustrating the journey from authentication to active workshop management.

The journey begins with secure authentication and workshop selection, followed by participant registration and workshop preparation activities. During active sessions, facilitators are guided through the methodology using structured agendas, contextual instructions, built-in timers, and supporting materials. Our system also enables real-time documentation through integrated photo capture and media upload capabilities, ensuring that workshop outputs can be recorded and organised in line with their pedagogical context.

This workflow-centred approach reflects the UC1's objective of combining methodological guidance with lightweight digital support. By integrating workshop management, participant administration, facilitation resources, and documentation tools into a single interface, the toolkit reduces operational overhead while preserving the collaborative and reflective nature of the Food Memories workshop process.

Figure 5: A facilitator walkthrough of various UIs of our Food Memories system.

2.1.7 Security, Data Sovereignty, and Governance

2.1.7.1 Authentication Security

The following security controls are implemented in the latest version of our system:

- *bcryptjs* with a cost factor of 12. Password complexity is enforced at both client (real-time validation) and server (regex check before hashing);
- One hour (configurable via `JWT_ACCESS_EXPIRES` environment variable). Short-lived tokens limit the impact of token leakage;
- Each refresh token use issues a new token and invalidates the previous one. Expired tokens are pruned from the user document on each login and refresh;
- Refresh tokens are stored in `httpOnly`, `SameSite=Lax` cookies, are inaccessible to JavaScript, and are protected against CSRF in same-site deployments;
- *Express-rate-limit* applies a global 300-request/15-minute window at the application level, and a stricter 20-request/15-minute window on all authentication endpoints;

- Helmet.js sets *Content-Security-Policy*, *X-Content-Type-Options*, *X-Frame-Options*, and related headers on all responses;
- *Express-validator* validates and sanitises all authentication inputs. Mongoose schema validation enforces types and required fields on all document writes.

An analysis of identified vulnerabilities and mitigation strategies is described in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Security vulnerability assessment for our Food Memories system.

VULNERABILITY	CURRENT STATUS	RECOMMENDED MITIGATION
CSRF on state-changing endpoints	Partially mitigated by <i>SameSite=Lax</i> cookie	Add CSRF token (<i>csrf</i> or double-submit cookie pattern) for production
No HTTPS enforcement	HTTP only in development	Terminate TLS at a reverse proxy (nginx + Let's Encrypt) for any network-accessible deployment
File path traversal	Mitigated by Multer's <i>diskStorage</i> (no user-controlled path components)	Add explicit path sanitisation if <i>moduleId</i> values are ever user-supplied without validation
Refresh token not salted before hashing	SHA-256 hash stored; collision risk negligible for 48-byte random tokens	Acceptable for current scope; consider HMAC with a server secret for defence-in-depth
No audit log	No record of who accessed, modified, or deleted data	Implement a write-ahead log (MongoDB change streams or a separate audit collection) for GDPR accountability
Photo file metadata (EXIF)	EXIF data (GPS, device) retained in uploaded images	Strip EXIF with Sharp or ExifTool before storage to prevent inadvertent geolocation disclosure

2.1.7.2 Data Sovereignty

Our system was designed with the following data sovereignty principles:

- All data defaults to the researcher's or facilitator's local machine. No data is transmitted to Anthropic, OpenAI, or any third party;
- The SPA does not include any analytics SDK (Google Analytics, Segment, etc.). The backend does not log request payloads;

- The MONGODB_URI and UPLOAD_ROOT environment variables allow the consortium to redirect storage to an institutional server or encrypted volume without code changes;
- The participant model collects only what is needed for workshop logistics (name, email, dietary needs, cultural background, notes). No biometric, location, or device data is collected programmatically.

2.1.7.3 GDPR Considerations

Our system handles personal data as defined in GDPR Article 4(1), including participant names, email addresses, and photographs. The following considerations apply to any consortium deployment:

- Processing should be grounded in consent (Article 6(1)(a)) or legitimate interests (Article 6(1)(f)). Consent should be obtained via the pre-circulated consent forms referenced in the workshop checklist;
- The participant DELETE endpoint (*DELETE /api/participants/:id*) supports the right to erasure (Article 17). Photo deletion (*DELETE /api/photos/:id*) removes both the metadata record and the file. No cascading deletion of associated workshop or user records is currently implemented; this should be added;
- No automated retention policy is implemented. Consortium members should establish and document a retention schedule and implement a scheduled deletion job;
- If the deployment is moved to a cloud provider, the standard contractual clauses and a data processing agreement with the provider are required under GDPR (V);
- The absence of an audit log (**Table 2**) complicates breach assessment. An audit log is recommended before any deployment involving sensitive participant data.

Figure 6: An overview of our Food Memories deployment using OpenStack.

2.1.7.4 Data Governance

The role hierarchy (participant < facilitator < admin) implements a governance model in which participants can only access their own uploads (they cannot view the roster or other participants' data), facilitators manage their own workshop and its associated participants and photos (they cannot access other facilitators' workshops), and administrators have cross-workshop visibility for monitoring, reporting, and data export purposes. Workshop archiving (soft-delete by facilitators) versus hard-deletion (admin-only) provides a two-stage governance mechanism: facilitators can close a workshop and release participants to the unassigned pool, whilst administrators retain the ability to permanently delete data when the retention period expires.

2.1.8 Deployment and Infrastructure

Our current system is deployed using a microservices multi-VM architecture via OpenStack (Figure 6).

2.1.9 Architectural Trade-offs

2.1.9.1 Strengths

Self-contained Deployability – Our entire stack (frontend, backend, database) runs on any web browser without external dependencies. A facilitator can operate the tool in a venue with internet access – a realistic setup in community or educational settings.

Data Sovereignty by Default – Workshop data – including personally identifiable participant information and photographs – is stored locally on the facilitator's machine. It syncs a copy to a database or object store hosted in our own dedicated infrastructure at IST. This aligns with RELISH's ethical and data management commitments and simplifies GDPR compliance.

Role-based Multi-tenancy – The three-role model (participant, facilitator, admin) and per-workshop data scoping support multi-facilitator deployments (e.g., consortium partners running parallel workshops) from a single server instance, without data cross-contamination.

Transparent Token Refresh – The *authFetch* abstraction provides a seamless user experience: access token expiry during a long workshop session does not disrupt the facilitator or require a re-login.

Pedagogically Structured Storage – Encoding day, phase, and module into the filesystem path means that the photo archive is self-documenting and can be browsed or exported by a researcher without the application.

2.1.9.2 Limitations and Risks

Monolithic Frontend Component – The single-component architecture (WorkshopTool, ~2,000 lines) will become a maintenance burden as features are added. State management for 40+ variables in a single component is fragile: re-renders triggered by any state change affect the entire tree, and debugging requires understanding the full state space. Refactoring into feature-specific sub-components and a shared context or state manager is a high-priority future task.

No Real-time Collaboration – The SPA does not support concurrent sessions: two facilitators accessing the same workshop simultaneously will experience stale data (last-write-wins on any mutation). For multi-facilitator deployments, a WebSocket or server-sent events layer would be required.

No Offline Resilience – The SPA communicates with the backend over HTTP; if the backend process crashes during a session, the facilitator loses access to all data-dependent features (participant roster, photos). A service worker and *IndexedDB* cache could provide offline resilience for read operations.

CRA Build Toolchain – The Create React App is in maintenance mode (no new features since 2022). Migration to Vite or Next.js is recommended for future iterations.

No Photo Compression or Video Support – Uploaded images are stored as-is. High-resolution camera photos (several megabytes each) will accumulate rapidly over the course of a two-day workshop with multiple participants. Server-side compression (e.g., Sharp library) should be added to the ingestion pipeline. Likewise, our system does not support video uploads that could illustrate, e.g., more verbal descriptions of recipes.

2.1.10 Summary and Future Work

This UC provides a functional, self-contained digital infrastructure for the RELISH Food Memories workshop methodology. It implements a three-tier web application with JWT-based authentication, role-scoped data access, persistent participant management, and a real-time photo documentation system. The architecture prioritises data sovereignty, local deployability, and alignment with the RELISH

project's ethical commitments. The current version is a working prototype that has been used to validate key technical requirements and to inform the iterative design process described in this section. The following directions are planned for subsequent versions of our system:

- Decompose *WorkshopTool* into feature-specific sub-components (*AgendaNavigator*, *ParticipantManager*, *PhotoLibrary*, *TimerPanel*, *AuthFlow*) and introduce a shared context or lightweight state manager;
- Add a *WebSocket* layer (*Socket.IO* or native *WS*) to synchronise workshop state across multiple facilitator sessions;
- Integrate *Sharp* for server-side image resizing and *EXIF* removal before storage;
- Implement a service worker and an *IndexedDB* cache to enable read-only access when the backend is unavailable;
- Add a write-ahead log (*MongoDB* change streams) for *GDPR* accountability and forensic analysis;
- Implement a structured export function that packages participant data, photos, and facilitation notes into a single archive (*ZIP* + *JSON* manifest) that can later be used to feed recipe knowledge bases;
- Migrate from *CRA* to *Vite* for faster development builds and a maintained toolchain.

2.2 UC3, T7.3: Recipes' Digital Twin

2.2.1 Introduction

Living traditions such as rituals, crafts, music, and foodways comprise Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) (Lenzerini 2011). Both a dimension of and in tension with cultural heritage (see **D3.1**), ICH plays a central role in shaping collective identity, social cohesion, and everyday practices, while being continuously recreated by communities in response to social, environmental, and cultural change (UNESCO 2003). Because ICH often elides documentation and representation due to its fluidity, tools or resources for recognising forms of ICH require mirroring practices that are dynamic, situated, and transmitted through participation. This poses significant challenges, as ICH is often informal, partially undocumented, and thus difficult to track in the context of globalisation and technological change, or in the face of interruptions to intergenerational knowledge transfer (Lenzerini 2011).

Digital twins (DTs) are a promising paradigm for cultural heritage preservation, offering 3D interactive representations that enable remote exploration and analysis (Luther et al. 2023). In domains such as manufacturing and smart cities, DTs typically serve as high-fidelity counterparts of physical assets, continuously updated through sensor data and used to support monitoring, prediction, and decision-making (Xu et al. 2024). Within cultural heritage, however, DT systems usually remain closer to static reconstructions or interactive archives, focusing primarily on the faithful reproduction of artefacts or sites (Amarilli et al. 2025; De Luca 2020).

ICH fundamentally challenges this paradigm. Unlike physical assets, ICH consists of living practices that change and migrate over time, vary across communities, and resist singular or authoritative representations (Zabulis et al. 2025). Capturing such practices requires shifting attention from objects to processes, from physical sensors to human activity, and from strict real-time synchronisation to rhythms shaped by social time (Sorokin and Merton 1937; Munn 1992; Lefebvre 2013; Bear 2016). As a result, existing DT approaches for cultural heritage offer limited support for modelling how ICH changes through everyday practice, reinterpretation, and participation.

In UC3, we explore how the DT paradigm can be adapted to better account for the distinctive characteristics of ICH. We ground our investigation in the domain of food culture, focusing on recipes as a form of intangible heritage that exemplifies continuous variation and cultural negotiation (Walschots 2023). Recipes are recognised as central to culinary traditions, yet they increasingly circulate through fragmented and decontextualised digital media, where they are constantly adapted and remixed (Steils and Obaidalaha 2020). This ongoing **recipe flux** makes them a

compelling case study for rethinking DTs as representations of evolving practices rather than fixed artefacts.

Building on this perspective, we introduce the first digital twin of a culinary recipe that leverages AI-based analysis of social media content to monitor real-world cooking practices in near real time. By structuring and aggregating digital traces of cooking activity, the proposed system enables the detection of variations, trends, and temporary stabilisations within culinary practices. Informed by a focus group session with HCI researchers and practitioners, we further outline potential applications and design opportunities enabled by recipe DTs, including interactive visual interfaces for exploring culinary heritage, participatory educational experiences, and sustainability-oriented decision support.

2.2.2 Modelling Intangible Cultural Heritage as a Digital Twin

Digital twins have traditionally been applied to physical assets, where the twin serves as a high-fidelity, real-time representation of the physical entity (Sun et al. 2022). In this context, sensors continuously monitor the object, data is synchronised in real-time, and the twin enables predictive maintenance, simulation, and optimisation (Tyagi and Richa 2023). Applying the DT paradigm to ICH, including culinary traditions, requires rethinking concepts of cultural heritage.

In this paradigm shift, the *twin subject* moves from material objects to cultural practices. Data sources, traditionally IoT devices or BIM/BMS, can be replaced by a *people-as-sensors* approach (Wang et al. 2014), in which human actors provide data through the digital traces of their practices. In the case of recipes, these traces include cooking videos, posts, and texts shared on social media platforms, blogs, or other online repositories. Synchronisation likewise departs from strict real-time updates. Instead, the ICH digital twin reflects changes in *social time* (Sorokin and Merton 1937; Munn 1992; Lefebvre 2013; Bear 2016), where periodic discovery and near-real-time ingestion of new content track the evolution of practices. Fidelity also takes on a plural form: multiple valid versions of a recipe can coexist, each recognised as authentic or acceptable by different communities. The same concept applies to other forms of ICH.

When modelling ICH as a digital twin, a fundamental distinction must be drawn between the cultural practice itself and its concrete manifestations (see **D4.1**³ on the interrelationships between material and intangible cultural heritage). Practices such as rituals, crafts, or culinary traditions exist as shared, evolving bodies of knowledge,

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/19922981>

while their enactments are situated, context-dependent, and often material. In culinary practice, this distinction is the difference between a dish and its recipe. While a dish is a materialised outcome of cooking, a recipe encodes procedural knowledge, ingredient relationships, and cultural meaning. Recipes obtained from curated sources, such as cookbooks or structured datasets, can provide relatively complete representations of culinary knowledge, but as **D5.1**⁴ workshops demonstrated, they often overlook oral and vernacular expressions.

Figure 7: The layered architecture of our recipe digital twin system.

By contrast, recipes shared through online platforms – e.g., social media videos – often convey knowledge in a more informal, fragmented manner, leaving many details implicit. Accordingly, a DT should capture a set of core recipe attributes, including ingredients with quantities and units, tools, and step-by-step instructions with timing when these properties can be reliably extracted (conceptualised in **D4.3**⁵ as recipe ontologies and semantic layers, and developed for historical recipe visualisations in **D3.3**⁶). With less comprehensive online sources, the system can instead leverage contextual metadata, such as the content’s geographic origin or the language in which the recipe is described. The model is intentionally extensible and can be enriched with

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/20967900>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/21013029>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/19374402>

additional dimensions, such as taste, nutritional value, environmental impact of ingredients, or community sentiment towards it.

This modelling approach is not without its challenges. Take reusing existing entities, such as ingredients and tools, across multiple recipes. For example, a single tomato entity may be shared as an ingredient between pizza and lasagna recipes, while still allowing for contextual variations in quantity and preparation. A related challenge concerns detecting when ingredients are themselves derived from other recipes, as could be the case of lasagna pasta sheets being modelled as a sub-recipe of lasagna rather than as a simple atomic ingredient. Enabling these capabilities streamlines computing *diffs* across various recipes or versions of the same recipe, facilitating the detection of emerging consensus within the community. Such capabilities are also vital for simulating potential recipe evolutions and predicting how culinary practices may change in response to cultural, environmental, or social factors.

2.2.3 Architecture

The architecture of our recipe DT (Figure 7) reflects the modelling principles defined in the previous subsection while maintaining modularity and extensibility. We adopted a layered approach that separates data acquisition, storage, modelling, and service provision:

- The **reality layer**, often referred to as the physical layer in traditional DTs, provides sources of culinary data, including social media platforms, cooking datasets, and other recipe repositories.
- The **ingestion layer** interfaces with these sources, extracting non-structured and semi-structured information such as videos, text, images, and metadata. The layer then converts data into a format compatible with the storage layer. This process involves parsing recipe content, identifying entities such as ingredients or tools, and reusing previously known entities where applicable.
- Informed by D4.3, the **storage layer** maintains all DT data, including current recipes, historical versions, and metadata for provenance tracking.
- A separate **modelling and prediction layer** interacts with the storage and service layers to perform analyses, trend detection, simulations, and forecasting.
- The **service layer** exposes the means to interact with the twin, such as APIs and command-line interfaces.

- Finally, the **app layer** includes all front-facing applications based on the DT that query, visualise, and manipulate recipe data.

2.2.4 Implementation

To test the feasibility of our approach, we developed a first prototype of the DT adhering to the presented architecture. The DT core is written in TypeScript and runs on Deno. System components can be deployed using Docker, and interaction with the DT is supported both locally via CLI or remotely through REST APIs exposed by the service layer. The prototype's source code is publicly available on GitHub.⁷

At the storage level, the prototype relies on a MongoDB cluster with semantic search capabilities. In addition to storing recipes, historical versions, and metadata, the database supports vector-based similarity search on ingredients and tools, which is used to identify existing entities that can be reused when ingesting new recipes. This capability is essential for maintaining consistency across the dataset and supporting the modelling challenges discussed earlier. Several AI components are used throughout the ingestion pipeline to extract structured information from unstructured and semi-structured sources. The system currently employs the following models: OpenAI Whisper-1⁸ for audio transcription of cooking videos; OpenAI GPT-4.1 for generating textual descriptions of selected video frames; OpenAI GPT-4o mini for text generation and structured data extraction; and OpenAI text-embedding-ada-002 for generating embeddings for semantic search.

YouTube currently serves as the data source to capture live recipe information via a dedicated adapter. For each identified cooking video, the system applies a multi-step processing pipeline that combines captions, audio transcripts, and video frame descriptions to infer ingredients, tools, and preparation steps. Extracted information is merged, validated, and stored, enabling the DT to evolve as new content becomes available online. The current implementation focuses on YouTube to showcase its capabilities, but new adapters can be easily developed to integrate additional data points – from other social media platforms to blogs and other online sources.

⁷ <https://github.com/gtumedei/relish-recipe-dt/releases/tag/v0.1.0>

⁸ <https://developers.openai.com/api/docs/models/whisper-1>

2.2.5 Design Opportunities

Modelling recipes as DTs opens a range of application scenarios beyond ICH preservation, enabling exploration, interpretation, and participation. This section presents a set of application concepts that emerged from an informal focus group activity. The activity involved four HCI researchers/practitioners and a facilitator: (i) the facilitator provided a brief introduction to the recipe DT concept and capabilities; (ii) participants independently wrote or sketched their ideas on a shared digital whiteboard; (iii) each participant presented their contributions to the group; and (iv) the group engaged in a final discussion. The ideas generated during are presented as two representative application concepts (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Speculative interface mock-ups of the application concepts emerged from our focus group session. From left to right: the *Culinary Practice Observatory* and the *Collaborative Recipe Studio*.

2.2.5.1 Culinary Practice Atlas

For policymakers, cultural institutions, and researchers

A web-based culinary practice atlas can provide tools to analyse and monitor how recipes and cooking practices evolve. Rather than treating recipes as isolated artefacts, the atlas visualises them as clusters of variants, allowing users to inspect how a dish changes across geography and time. Interactive maps and timelines reveal regional adaptations, emerging trends, and shared cores among variants, with normalised visual representations that abstract away differences in source format (e.g., video versus text). Visual dashboards summarise indicators such as changing ingredient usage,

preparation techniques, or tool adoption, enabling the detection of viral trends, the emergence of potentially unhealthy or unsustainable behaviours, and broader patterns of homogenization or diversification that are relevant to food policy and sustainability research (Zhou et al. 2022).

Building on the predictive capabilities of DTs (Bhatia and Kumar 2025), the atlas should also support simulation and scenario exploration, allowing stakeholders to pose *what-if* questions, such as how ingredient shortages, price changes, or sustainability campaigns might influence recipe evolution. By explicitly linking analytical views and simulations to the underlying data, the atlas can present clear evidence that supports transparent decision-making and effective communication with the public, which increasingly relies on longitudinal, interpretable data (Boone et al. 2025).

2.2.5.2 Collaborative Research Studio

For cooks, educators, culinary students, and casual users

Research in food HCI highlights the importance of participatory and narrative-based approaches for engaging people with food practices and cultural knowledge (Gayler et al. 2022; Altarriba Bertran et al. 2019). The recipe digital twin enables such approaches through an application that combines mobile interaction with eXtended Reality (XR). On mobile devices, users can search and discover recipes based on contextual information such as available ingredients, seasonality, current trends, or dietary practices, reflecting growing interest in context-aware cooking support (Starychfojtu and Peska 2020). They can also contribute new recipes in any format, including text, video, audio description, or photographs of cookbook pages, which the DT automatically converts to a structured format and incorporates. Users may even create pop-culture recipes inspired by movies or video games, which are grounded in real-world culinary practices by mapping them onto similar ingredients and patterns observed by the DT. For educators, the studio enables the curation of interactive, story-driven cookbooks that trace the evolution of a dish, compare similar recipes across cultures, or highlight seasonal and historical transformations, aligning with prior work on food storytelling for learning (Davis et al. 2014).

XR extends these capabilities with DT-mediated cook-together sessions, in which physically distant participants prepare the same recipe while observing each other's actions in a shared virtual space. Educators can lead remote cooking classes in this environment, guide learners step by step, and provide tailored suggestions. The DT structures the recipe, supervises execution, adapts guidance based on individual users' needs and ingredient availability, and records the outcome as new instantiations of the prepared recipe. In this way, hands-on learning, social collaboration, and storytelling all

directly feed back into the evolution of the DT, enriching practical cooking with exploration, reflection, and cultural interpretation.

2.2.6 Summary and Future Work

In this UC we explored extending the DT paradigm beyond physical assets to represent ICH as living, evolving artefacts. Using culinary recipes as a case study, we propose a layered architecture that shifts the focus from objects to practices, treating digital traces of human activity as sensor data. We present a prototype that integrates online data sources and AI-based analysis to model recipes as dynamic entities. Through a set of application scenarios derived from a focus group session, we highlighted how recipe digital twins enable new opportunities for visual exploration, discussion, participation, and social interaction, ultimately supporting the preservation and transmission of culinary heritage.

Future work will focus on consolidating and extending the proposed system. We will finalise and deploy the prototype as a foundation for application development and expand the model to include additional dimensions, such as community sentiment, nutritional value, and environmental impact. The system will also be evaluated on a broader and more diverse recipe corpus to refine data extraction, modelling, and comparison methods, drawing on technical developments from **D3.3**, ontology considerations for **D4.3**, and methodological frameworks from **D5.1**. Beyond technical development, we will engage relevant stakeholders through participatory activities (e.g., focus groups and co-design sessions) to identify needs and visions, and use these insights to select and implement one or more case studies exploring the design space of digital twins for cICH.

2.3 UC4, T7.5: Shopping Recommender: Seasonality and Preferred Cuisines

2.3.1 Introduction

In recent years, increasing attention has been devoted to more sustainable and informed food consumption, particularly regarding the environmental and nutritional implications of everyday dietary choices. Within this broader shift, **seasonal eating** encourages consuming ingredients at their natural peak of availability and can offer benefits in nutrition, sustainability, and affordability. Seasonal produce can be fresher, more flavourful, and, in many cases, more nutritious, while also supporting dietary variety throughout the year. At the same time, eating in season can reduce reliance on energy-intensive production systems and long-distance transportation, thereby helping to lower environmental impact and food waste (Macdiarmid 2014; Cleghorn and Reynolds 2022).

In parallel, computational gastronomy is a data-driven approach to studying recipes, ingredients, and cuisines, drawing on methods from network science, statistics, and machine learning (Goel and Bagler 2022). This field has shown that culinary patterns can be modelled in structured and interpretable ways, revealing how ingredients interact across food cultures and how cuisines differ in their internal organisation. In particular, graph-based approaches have been used to model ingredient co-occurrence, ingredient types, and recipe similarity, offering a solid foundation for recommendation systems and culinary analysis (Magyari-Sáska et al. 2026; Bellingeri et al. 2025; Caprioli et al. 2025).

UC4 addresses two needs: (i) promoting seasonal produce in everyday diets and (ii) providing computational tools for analysing culinary structure. We developed a seasonal ingredient recommendation system designed to raise awareness of seasonal produce available in Europe year-round and simplify grocery shopping for users. The user selects an anchor ingredient among those currently in season in their area, and the system identifies the cuisines that make most use of it before recommending a coherent set of complementary ingredients. The aim is for our system to propose ingredient sets that pair well with both the anchor ingredient and one another, encouraging users to experiment more confidently with seasonal cooking and, over time, to make seasonal ingredients part of everyday or spontaneous purchasing habits.

Figure 9: Plots displaying *Italian cuisine*'s graph edge weights before normalisation (showing scale-free characteristics), applying a $1/k$ normalisation, and the log-normalisation used in the UC.

2.3.2 System Design

In the first stage of our system design and implementation, we used a dataset on seasonality⁹ that, for a substantial set of fruit and vegetables, indicates, for each month and each country, whether an item is in season. This allowed us to compute a seasonality score ranging from 0 to 1, where 0 corresponds to an ingredient that is entirely out of season and 1 to an ingredient that is fully seasonal in the user's location. Intermediate values reflect both temporal proximity to the in-season period and whether the ingredient is seasonal elsewhere, a distinction that is relevant because the environmental impact of imported produce depends not only on distance but also on the mode of transport.

In the second stage, we built ingredient co-occurrence graphs for multiple cuisines worldwide (Figure 9). In this framework, ingredient pairing frequency across recipes is used to capture how strongly ingredients are associated within a given culinary tradition, independently of chemical composition or other external factors. These networks are initially constructed from raw co-occurrence counts and typically display scale-free characteristics, with a small number of highly connected nodes and many sparsely connected ones. Following prior work on weighted culinary networks, such values can be normalised to achieve more homogeneous edge weights across networks of different sizes and to reduce bias introduced by recipe length or network density (Barabási and Bonabeau 2003).

⁹ <https://www.eufic.org/en/explore-seasonal-fruit-and-vegetables-in-europe>

Figure 10: Our web application displaying the connections for cucumbers in *Japanese cuisine*. The ingredient recommendations are shown in the left column, while seasonality scores are shown in the right column.

We then enriched these networks with seasonality scores by adjusting ingredient-node relevance according to how seasonal each ingredient is in the user’s location. Ingredients with high seasonality receive a positive adjustment, while out-of-season ingredients receive a penalty, resulting in a network that more explicitly represents both culinary relevance and seasonal availability. This step makes seasonality an integral part of the recommendation process rather than an external filter applied after the fact.

2.3.3 Recommender

To retrieve the most relevant ingredients to pair with a seasonal anchor item, we first located the item in the network and retained only its strongest connections above a predefined threshold. We then extracted a clique from this subnetwork to ensure that the recommended ingredients are not only strongly related to the anchor ingredient but also mutually compatible. A clique-based step, rather than an individually plausible system, supports structurally cohesive recommendations. In practice, it enables our system to propose ingredient sets that serve as a usable culinary basis across multiple meals.

Before presenting the final set of ingredients to the user, we also examined the typical structure of recipes involving the selected seasonal ingredient. In particular, we analysed the food type graph, which captures how ingredient categories combine across recipes and provides a coarse-grained view of culinary structure. Lastly, we estimate the average composition of food types in recipes containing the seasonal anchor ingredient, thereby offering users an additional layer of interpretative information when shopping for unfamiliar ingredients. This allows users shop with greater confidence for a small number of meals built around the seasonal item.

Figure 11: Our Telegram bot interface for the ingredient recommender. *From left to right*: the user first receives a list of all seasonal items with their seasonality score, then chooses an ingredient and a cuisine from which to get recommendations.

2.3.4 Interface Design

At present, our system is accessible through two interfaces designed for different end-users: a **Telegram bot** (@ingredient_recommendation_bot) that supports direct, lightweight interaction and allows users to obtain the necessary information quickly while shopping (Figure 11); and a **web application** that, by contrast, is intended to display the underlying architecture more explicitly, showing how ingredients interact

within each cuisine through the graphs (Figure 10). This interface is designed as a dashboard for food studies researchers examining the specific characteristics of each cuisine and integrating seasonality into their analysis.

2.3.5 System Implementation

The core components of our recommender system were implemented in Python, using the Pandas,¹⁰ NumPy,¹¹ and Matplotlib¹² libraries for data processing, numerical analysis, and visualisation. The graph-based architecture was developed with NetworkX.¹³ Starting from the RecipeDB dataset,¹⁴ the recipe collection was first transformed into a bipartite recipe-ingredient graph. The graph was then projected into the ingredient co-occurrence graphs described in the previous sections. In our implementation recipe knowledge is represented by a recipe-ingredient bipartite graph and an ingredient-ingredient co-occurrence graph.

Seasonality information was integrated from the European Food Information Council (EUFIC) dataset on seasonal fruit and vegetables in Europe. The Telegram bot was implemented using the python-telegram-bot library¹⁵ and organised around a four-state *ConversationHandler*, which guides the user through the recommendation pipeline step by step: nation selection, month input, anchor ingredient choice, and cuisine selection. For security, the bot token is loaded from an environment file via python-dotenv.¹⁶

Lastly, our web interface of interactive graphs was developed in JavaScript and D3.¹⁷ The backend server, responsible for handling API calls between the interface and the recommender engine, was implemented in Python using standard libraries, as the application requires only a limited number of endpoints.

2.3.6 Summary and Future Work

For UC4 we have developed a graph-based seasonal ingredient recommendation system that integrates seasonality information with computational gastronomy to support more informed and sustainable food choices and research support. Starting

¹⁰ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

¹¹ <https://numpy.org/>

¹² <https://matplotlib.org/>

¹³ <https://networkx.org/en/>

¹⁴ <https://cosylab.iiitd.edu.in/recipe-db/>

¹⁵ <https://python-telegram-bot.org/>

¹⁶ <https://pypi.org/project/python-dotenv/>

¹⁷ <https://d3js.org/>

from a seasonal dataset and a cuisine-specific network representation, the system identifies an anchor ingredient, retrieves the cuisines that best exploit it, and recommends a coherent set of complementary ingredients, while also exposing the underlying structure of ingredient interactions and food-type composition.

Beyond single-ingredient queries, multi-ingredient recommendations are also currently in development. In this future work, our system takes a set of ingredients as input and first evaluates how well they interact within each cuisine, as well as which cuisine makes the best use of them. Once a suitable cuisine is identified, the same graph-based framework is used to identify additional ingredients that strongly connect with the set, thereby proposing a shopping list or pairing that better supports and completes the recipes. This direction builds on the existing architecture, since it relies on the same ingredient co-occurrence graphs, but shifts the focus from a single anchor to a more flexible and realistic multi-item query.

More generally, UC4 demonstrates how culinary knowledge can be encoded in graph form and used not only to recommend ingredients but also to make the structure of cuisines more interpretable. By combining seasonality with co-occurrence strength, cohesion, and food-type composition, our system moves beyond simple ingredient popularity and preliminarily captures the **relational logic behind recipes**. The results also indicate the limits of the current implementation, which still focuses primarily on seasonality and cuisine-specific ingredient compatibility.

For this reason, future development would broaden our approach beyond seasonality alone. The same architecture could incorporate nutritional facts, allergens, dietary constraints, and greenhouse gas emissions, turning the system into a more comprehensive meal-planning tool (Dong et al. 2026). The recommender model could provide a holistic approach to help users make healthier, safer, and more environmentally responsible choices.

Ultimately, UC4 is a step toward a more complete ingredient intelligence system. The current version already demonstrates that graph-based recommendations can make seasonal shopping more accessible and culinary exploration more coherent, while the planned extensions open the way to a broader platform for meal planning, dietary support, and sustainability-aware food decision-making.

2.4 UC5, T7.6: Youth Survey on Food Culture

2.4.1 Introduction

What people eat, cook, and remember is closely bound up with identity, belonging, and the negotiation between tradition and change (Fischler 1988). However, there are few comprehensive studies on how particular generations, especially emerging adults, characterise their food traditions and cultures, and in turn, useful data on how to identify contemporary impacts on these characterisations and everyday food practices (see **D3.2**¹⁸). Understanding how communities, and young people in particular, relate to food culture is therefore central to RELISH's ambition of safeguarding and reframing European gastronomic heritage.

In UC5, we designed and deployed a family of online surveys that capture how primarily young people describe their food practices, culinary identity, and expectations for the future, and we paired each survey with a bespoke interactive dashboard to explore its responses.

Our system hosts three surveys, a **Food & Culture Questionnaire**,¹⁹ a **Futures Survey**,²⁰ and a **Futures Visions/Images About the Future exercise**,²¹ each coupled with a dedicated dashboard: the Youth dashboard,²² the Futures dashboard,²³ and the Narratives dashboard.²⁴ All three aimed at recruitment and responses among emerging adults. The instruments differ in both content and form:

- **Food & Culture Questionnaire** – This is the most extensive instrument (73 items). It covers demographics, cooking habits and confidence, household arrangements, iconic and everyday dishes, key ingredients, food-related social-media use, dietary preferences, and the role of food in personal, regional, and national identity.
- **The Futures Survey** – This survey combines a short demographic profile with ordinal (Likert-style) judgements about the respondent's outlook for themselves, their country, Europe, and the world, across dimensions such as technology, the economy, the ecosystem, politics, security, society, and culture.

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/19472257>

¹⁹ https://relish-platform.eu/youth_survey

²⁰ https://relish-platform.eu/futures_survey

²¹ https://relish-platform.eu/futures_narratives

²² https://relish-platform.eu/youth_dashboard

²³ https://relish-platform.eu/futures_dashboard

²⁴ https://relish-platform.eu/futures_narratives_dashboard

- **Food Visions/Images About the Future exercise** – This is largely an open-ended survey that invites participants to write a short narrative, “A Day in the Life in 2050,” alongside a brief profile, eliciting rich qualitative visions of everyday food futures.

To date, we have collected 877 responses across the three instruments: 475 in the Food & Culture Questionnaire, 200 in the Futures Survey, and 202 in the Food Visions/Images About the Future exercise. These responses form the corpus that the dashboards make explorable and that grounds the analysis discussed below. This section describes the surveys and their visualisations, the architecture connecting them, the implementation, and the privacy and security measures protecting participant data, before outlining directions for more experiential visual interfaces. The qualitative survey design, rationale, and preliminary results are discussed in **D3.2: “RELISH Youth Survey and Results Collected for Analysis.”**

Figure 12: The three-tier architecture of our surveys includes a security and privacy layer that spans the presentation, application, and storage tiers.

2.4.2 Architecture

The surveys follow a classic three-tier organisation that cleanly separates presentation, application logic, and storage:

- **The presentation tier** is a single-page web application that serves both roles of the system: it renders the three surveys from declarative definitions and hosts the three dashboards, so that a participant and an analyst use the same application but follow different routes.
- **The application tier** exposes a small API: a write path that receives and validates survey submissions, and a read path that returns, for a given survey, a filtered and privacy-preserving view of its responses.
- **The storage tier** persists every submission as a structured document, with one collection per survey type so that the three instruments remain cleanly partitioned.

Two design decisions shape the data flow. First, **each dashboard is bound to a single survey**: it requests only that specific survey's responses and renders them through views tailored to the instrument. The Youth dashboard offers a broad, coordinated, multi-view exploration of youth responses, including a world map of geographic origins and a large set of linked charts spanning demographics, cooking practices, dishes, ingredients, and food identity (Figure 14). The Futures dashboard presents a respondent profile alongside ordinal bar charts that summarise the four-point outlook and six-point relevance items. The Narratives dashboard pairs a profile with a searchable reader for the "A Day in the Life in 2050" texts. Second, a **normalisation step** reconciles open-text answers, dishes, ingredients, regular dishes, "desert-island" foods, and social-media handles into canonical entities; the dashboards join the raw responses with these pre-computed normalisation tables in the browser, so the analytical views always reflect that pre-processing without performing it on demand.

Cross-cutting the tiers is a **security and privacy layer**. The public read path exposes only the data the dashboards need, with direct identifiers removed; bulk export of raw responses is restricted to authenticated administrators; activity logs record only anonymised client information; and the write path validates every submission against the survey's expected shape. These measures are detailed in the next subsection.

2.4.3 Implementation

The **front-end** is a single-page React application. The surveys are built with a declarative survey toolkit, while the dashboards are composed from standard charting and cartographic libraries, bar, line, and area charts, distribution plots, and TopoJSON world maps for geographic origin. The **back-end** is a Node.js/Express service backed by MongoDB, with one collection per survey type. In production, both services run behind

an nginx reverse proxy that terminates TLS, and process management is handled by pm2. The whole system is hosted on a virtual machine (VM) in our institution’s (IST) cloud services, which isolates the execution environment and ensures predictable performance; backups are kept on a separate IST server to safeguard the collected responses. The presentation tier is fully responsive and adapted for mobile devices, so that both the surveys and the dashboards can be completed and explored on smartphones and tablets as well as on desktop computers (Figure 13).

Figure 13: How our three surveys render responsively across desktop, laptop, and mobile devices.

An AI model supports the data pipeline as an offline preprocessing step; the model is not invoked when a dashboard is viewed. Anthropic’s Claude **normalises noisy free-text** food data, canonicalising the many spellings and phrasings of dishes, ingredients, regular dishes, “desert-island” foods, and social-media handles into consistent entities; the resulting look-up tables are consumed directly by the dashboards, most extensively by the Youth dashboard.

A defence-in-depth **security layer** protects participant data. Administrative endpoints, most importantly the raw bulk export, require a bearer token; the service compares this token in constant time and fails closed when it is unset. The public dashboard feed strips direct identifiers (e.g., e-mail and participant identifier) before any response

leaves the server. Our system never stores client IP addresses in the clear; it reduces them to salted, one-way hashes. The API rate-limits requests per client, size-caps and sanitises request bodies against database-operator injection, and validates every submission against a per-survey schema, so that callers cannot use the public submission endpoint to inject spurious or malformed data. Both Node services bind to *localhost* and accept connections only through the TLS proxy, which applies standard security headers to every response.

Figure 14: *Left*: The Youth dashboard, mapping the geographic origin of respondents alongside a ranked list of countries. *Right*: The Narratives dashboard, offering a searchable reader for the “A Day in the Life in 2050” responses.

2.4.4 Summary and Future Work

This UC has delivered a deployed, operational system. We designed and built three surveys on food culture and food futures, each paired with a bespoke dashboard, together with the application and storage infrastructure that connects them and a privacy-preserving data pipeline that turns noisy free-text into analysable, anonymised data. The platform is already live and has collected 877 responses across the three instruments; each instrument can be explored immediately at both the individual and aggregate levels.

Analytical use of the dashboards – Beyond serving as participant-facing companions, the per-survey dashboards already function as analytical instruments. Their coordinated, linked views support exploratory data analysis (EDA) across the collected corpus, allowing us to inspect distributions, cross-tabulate demographic and behavioural variables, and surface patterns, contrasts, and recurrences across the food-culture and futures data. We have begun this exploratory phase and will extend it

as the response set grows, using it both to characterise the data and to identify questions worth pursuing.

Towards richer, more experiential visualisations – Building on this analysis, our main future work is to move from faithful, analyst-oriented views towards visual forms that convey the data's cultural richness to broader, non-expert audiences. We are approaching this as a design study (Sedlmair et al. 2012): rather than committing to a finished component up front, we will characterise tasks and refine our research questions through structured engagement with our colleagues at UA and FA and with target users, then iterate through a sequence of low- to high-fidelity prototypes that we design, test, and either discard or refine. Narrative-driven and playful registers are the most promising directions to explore: guided scrollytelling that balances author-driven structure with reader-driven exploration in the spirit of data-driven storytelling (Segel and Heer 2010); and lightweight, gamified interactions that frame exploration as play (Sweetser and Wyeth 2005). We are already developing a **scrollytelling prototype** that pairs an explanatory narrative thread with free exploration of the underlying responses, designed to make the data more engaging and easier to interpret than the current analyst-oriented dashboards.

Evaluation – We will evaluate our survey prototypes with target users through a mixed-methods protocol that combines standardised questionnaires with qualitative inquiry. Quantitatively, we will measure engagement and perceived cognitive load, complemented by measures of comprehension and of how strongly users identify with, and recognise their own food culture in the visualisations. Qualitatively, think-aloud sessions and semi-structured interviews will surface where the narrative supports or hinders understanding, whether users agree with the patterns surfaced, and which forms best convey the richness of the underlying food-culture data. These findings will drive the selection and refinement of the forms to which we ultimately commit.

3 Conclusions

D7.2 demonstrates the substantive progress of the RELISH web platform in supporting the project's overarching goal of preserving and revitalising European culinary heritage. By employing a federated System of Systems (SoS) architecture hosted on a private cloud, the platform successfully balances the need for systemic fault tolerance with strict institutional data governance and sovereignty. The four use-cases detailed in this report – ranging from the **Food Memories facilitator app** (UC1) and the **AI-driven Recipes' Digital Twin** (UC3), to the graph-based **Shopping Recommender** (UC4) and the interactive dashboards of the **Youth Survey on Food Culture** (UC5) – illustrate how the platform integrates digital innovation with tangible and intangible cultural practices. Together, these autonomous systems provide scalable tools that foster social connection, promote sustainable eating habits, and capture the evolving nature of everyday gastronomy. Likewise, they better capture the dynamic reality of culinary recipes, which we refer to as **recipe flux**.

Looking ahead, the iterative design and implementation work documented here lays a robust foundation for the platform's continued evolution, leading up to the complete use-case report scheduled for September 2027 (M33). Until then, the IST team will continue to expand the UC above while engaging in two novel UCs. The first, **UC2**, will lead to an **interactive map** for the web based on the food sustainability impact data (T3.4) and survey data (T3.2, T3.3) describing the food practices of young people and wider population in Europe (e.g., type of food, social context), and the expected environmental impact of these food practices (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions, water footprint). The second, **UC6**, will lead to a **spatial computing, AI cooking companion**. We will target commercial smartglasses via a proof-of-concept prototype that detects and responds to everyday cooking actions and items. Users should not only be guided towards a specific goal (e.g., completing a recipe), but also receive relevant information such as nutritional or historical information regarding a recipe item in their hands.

By continually testing and extending these tools through participatory activities and pilot workshops, the RELISH consortium is well-positioned to deliver a comprehensive digital ecosystem that meaningfully safeguards and reframes culinary heritage for both researchers and the general public.

Bibliography

- Altarriba Bertran, Ferran, Samvid Jhaveri, Rosa Lutz, Katherine Isbister, and Danielle Wilde. 2019. 'Making Sense of Human-Food Interaction'. *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, CHI '19, May, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300908>.
- Amarilli, Fabrizio, Matthias Alfeld, and Gian Piero Zarri. 2025. 'An Advanced Digital Twin Approach for Iconographic Heritage Modeling and Processing'. *Proceedings of the 7th International Workshop on AnalySis, Understanding and ProMotion of HeritAge Contents*, October, 79–87. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3746273.3760208>.
- Barabási, Albert-László, and Eric Bonabeau. 2003. 'Scale-Free Networks'. *Scientific American* 288 (5): 60–69.
- Bear, Laura. 2016. 'Time as Technique'. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 45 (Volume 45, 2016): 487–502. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-102313-030159>.
- Bellingeri, Michele, Axel Bidon-Chanal Badia, Marta Vila Rigat, Roberto Alfieri, Massimiliano Turchetto, and Davide Cassi. 2025. 'The Recipe Similarity Network: A New Algorithm to Extract Relevant Information from Cookbooks'. *Scientific Reports* 15 (1): 34380. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-17189-6>.
- Bhatia, Munish, and Vijay Kumar. 2025. 'Bibliometric Study of Digital Twin for Sustainable Cities and Society'. *ACM Journal on Computing and Sustainable Societies* 3 (4): 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3748820>.
- Boone, Ashley, Aparna Arul, James Kemerait, et al. 2025. 'Designing Tools for Data Advocacy'. *Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference*, DIS '25, July, 2130–42. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3715336.3735801>.
- Caprioli, Claudio, Saumitra Kulkarni, Federico Battiston, Iacopo Iacopini, Andrea Santoro, and Vito Latora. 2025. 'The Networks of Ingredient Combinations as Culinary Fingerprints of World Cuisines'. *Npj Science of Food* 9 (1): 242. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41538-025-00588-4>.
- Cleghorn, Christine L., and Christian J. Reynolds. 2022. 'Importance of Sustainable Food Environments'. In *Transforming Food Environments*. CRC Press.
- Davis, Hilary, Bjorn Nansen, Frank Vetere, et al. 2014. 'Homemade Cookbooks: A Recipe for Sharing'. *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Designing Interactive Systems*, DIS '14, June, 73–82. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2598510.2598590>.
- De Luca, Livio. 2020. 'Towards the Semantic-Aware 3D Digitisation of Architectural Heritage: The "Notre-Dame de Paris" Digital Twin Project'. *Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Structuring and Understanding of Multimedia HeritAge Contents*, MM '20, October, 3–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3423323.3423415>.
- Dong, Xiaolan, Bei Yun, Anni Pakarinen, et al. 2026. 'Diet-Related Health Recommender Systems for Patients With Chronic Health Conditions: Scoping Review'. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 28 (1): e77726. <https://doi.org/10.2196/77726>.
- Fischler, Claude. 1988. 'Food, Self and Identity'. *Social Science Information* 27 (2): 275–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/053901888027002005>.
- Gayler, Tom, Corina Sas, and Vaiva Kalnikaitė. 2022. 'Exploring the Design Space for Human-Food-Technology Interaction: An Approach from the Lens of Eating Experiences'. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction* 29 (2): 1–52. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3484439>.
- Goel, Mansi, and Ganesh Bagler. 2022. 'Computational Gastronomy: A Data Science Approach to Food'. *Journal of Biosciences* 47 (1): 12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12038-021-00248-1>.
- Heldke, Lisa. 1988. 'Recipes for Theory Making'. *Hypatia* 3 (2): 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.1988.tb00066.x>.

- J.Lewis, Patrick, and Katia Hildebrandt. 2019. *Storytelling as Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526421036754858>.
- Josselson, Ruthellen, and Phillip L. Hammack. 2021. *Essentials of Narrative Analysis*. American Psychological Association.
- Lefebvre, Henri. 2013. *Rhythmanalysis: Space, Time and Everyday Life*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Lenzerini, F. 2011. 'Intangible Cultural Heritage: The Living Culture of Peoples'. *European Journal of International Law* 22 (1): 101–20. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chr006>.
- Luther, Wolfram, Nelson Baloian, Daniel Biella, and Daniel Sacher. 2023. 'Digital Twins and Enabling Technologies in Museums and Cultural Heritage: An Overview'. *Sensors* 23 (3): 1583. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23031583>.
- Macdiarmid, Jennie I. 2014. 'Seasonality and Dietary Requirements: Will Eating Seasonal Food Contribute to Health and Environmental Sustainability?' *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society* 73 (3): 368–75. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0029665113003753>.
- Magyari-Sáska, Zsolt, Attila Magyari-Sáska, and Lóránt Bálint-Bálint. 2026. 'From Cookbooks to Networks: A Framework for Comparing Multiethnic Ingredient Systems in Transylvania'. *Foods* 15 (6): 1006. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods15061006>.
- Mahmood, Asif. 2016. "'SoS Call" at the Other Edge of Chaos'. *Journal of Systems Science and Complexity* 29 (1): 133–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11424-015-3189-y>.
- Munn, Nancy D. 1992. 'The Cultural Anthropology of Time: A Critical Essay'. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 21: 93–123. JSTOR.
- Ricoeur, Paul. 2002. 'La Mémoire, l'Histoire, L'Oubli'. *Tijdschrift Voor Filosofie* 64 (1): 197–98.
- Savinetti, Nicol, Sez Kristiansen, and Sacramento Roselló Martínez. 2020. 'Stitching IMMART: Overcoming the Challenge of Inclusion Without Exclusion Through the Arts'. In *Fostering Pluralism through Solidarity Activism in Europe: Everyday Encounters with Newcomers*, edited by Feyzi Baban and Kim Rygiel. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56894-8_6.
- Sedlmair, Michael, Miriah Meyer, and Tamara Munzner. 2012. 'Design Study Methodology: Reflections from the Trenches and the Stacks'. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 18 (12): 2431–40. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2012.213>.
- Segel, Edward, and Jeffrey Heer. 2010. 'Narrative Visualization: Telling Stories with Data'. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 16 (6): 1139–48. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2010.179>.
- Sorokin, Pitirim A., and Robert K. Merton. 1937. 'Social Time: A Methodological and Functional Analysis'. *American Journal of Sociology* 42 (5): 615–29. <https://doi.org/10.1086/217540>.
- Starychfojtu, Josef, and Ladislav Peska. 2020. 'SmartRecepies: Towards Cooking and Food Shopping Integration via Mobile Recipes Recommender System'. *Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Information Integration and Web-Based Applications & Services, iiWAS '20*, November, 144–48. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3428757.3429096>.
- Steils, Nadia, and Zakia Obaidalahe. 2020. "'Social Food": Food Literacy Co-Construction and Distortion on Social Media'. *Food Policy* 95 (August): 101932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101932>.
- Sun, Wen, Wenqiang Ma, Yu Zhou, and Yan Zhang. 2022. 'An Introduction to Digital Twin Standards'. *GetMobile: Mobile Computing and Communications* 26 (3): 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3568113.3568119>.
- Sweetser, Penelope, and Peta Wyeth. 2005. 'GameFlow: A Model for Evaluating Player Enjoyment in Games'. *Computers in Entertainment (CIE)* 3 (3): 3. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1077246.1077253>.

- Tyagi, Amit Kumar and Richa. 2023. 'Digital Twin Technology: Opportunities and Challenges for Smart Era's Applications'. *Proceedings of the 2023 Fifteenth International Conference on Contemporary Computing, IC3 2023*, August, 328–36. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3607947.3608015>.
- UNESCO. 2003. 'Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage'. <https://ich.unesco.org/en/convention>.
- Walschots, Michael. 2023. 'A Philosophy of Recipes: Making, Experiencing, and Valuing. Edited by Andrea Borghini and Patrik Engisch. London: Bloomsbury Academic. 2022'. *Food Ethics* 8 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41055-023-00130-w>.
- Wang, Dong, Md Tanvir Amin, Shen Li, et al. 2014. 'Using Humans as Sensors: An Estimation-Theoretic Perspective'. *IPSN-14 Proceedings of the 13th International Symposium on Information Processing in Sensor Networks*, April, 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ipsn.2014.6846739>.
- Wells, Kathleen. 2011. *Narrative Inquiry*. Oxford University Press.
- Xu, Qianwen, Jingchao Wang, Wei Gao, Shuangyin Ren, and Zhongbo Li. 2024. 'Digital Twin: State-of-the-Art and Future Perspectives'. *Proceeding of the 2024 5th International Conference on Computer Science and Management Technology, ICCSMT 2024*, October, 731–40. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3708036.3708159>.
- Zabulis, Xenophon, Nikolaos Partarakis, Emmanouil Zidianakis, and Danae Kaplanidi. 2025. 'A Critical Review of the Function of Intangible Cultural Heritage as a Driver for Social Resilience and Cohesion'. *Encyclopedia* 5 (4): 189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/encyclopedia5040189>.
- Zhou, Bingjie, Shiwei Liang, Kyle M. Monahan, et al. 2022. 'Food and Nutrition Systems Dashboards: A Systematic Review'. *Advances in Nutrition* 13 (3): 748–57. <https://doi.org/10.1093/advances/nmac022>.